

relative humidity [RH]) and long-term (-10 °C, 30% RH) storerooms for periodic monitoring of seed viability, and monitoring every 5 yr for the medium-term and every 10 yr for the long-term storage. These intervals follow the longevity patterns of the control varieties.

Subtropical and temperate zone varieties stored earlier were regenerated as a batch in 1973-74, before average viability dropped to 50%. Tropical varieties were rejuvenated at later intervals.

This is the longest, continuously monitored seed storage experiment on record, but the control seed lots are now running low. ■

Genetics

Combining ability of some rice cultivars with selected cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines

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We studied the general combining ability (GCA) of 18 parents and the specific combining ability (SCA) of 45 crosses in a 15 (line) × 3 (tester) mating design: 12 varieties and 3 male fertility restorer lines used as pollen parents were crossed with 3 CMS lines.

The 63 treatments (15 lines, 3 testers, and 45 F₁s) were laid out in a completely randomized block design with three replications during 1985 wet season under irrigation. Experimental plots were three 3-m-long rows. Row and plant spacing was kept at 20 × 15 cm. Five competitive plants were randomly selected from each plot for analysis.

Male fertility restorer line IET5656 was the best general combiner for grain yield, followed by Narendra 80, IR54, Z97 A, and T26 (Table 1). Madhuri and Sattari exhibited good GCA effect for test weight. Narendra 80 and Pankaj were good general combiners for tiller number; IR54 and T26 were good for plant height. Sattari and Narendra 80 and female line IR46829 A were good general combiners for early heading.

Table 1. General combining ability for grain yield and other characters of some parental lines.^a

Parents	Plant height	Heading date	Tiller number	Test weight	Grain yield
<i>CMS female lines</i>					
V20 A	-1.54*	-0.49	0.64	-2.41**	0.28
IR46829 A	-14.48**	-2.32**	-3.78**	-2.33**	-3.75*
Z97 A	16.02**	2.82**	3.14**	-0.07	3.47**
<i>Male lines</i>					
<i>Male fertility restorer lines</i>					
IR50	3.16*	4.34**	-0.16	-2.41*	2.22**
IR54	17.12**	15.25**	4.82**	0.69	9.32**
IET5656	8.35**	8.89**	5.11**	-0.30	20.77**
<i>Non-fertility restorer varieties</i>					
Sattari	-11.90**	-15.53**	-11.77**	2.95**	-17.83**
Narendra 80	-4.20*	-3.53*	10.75**	0.57	10.73**
Pankaj	1.86	7.27**	10.29**	-0.57	-10.05**
T26	20.13**	14.25**	-2.62**	-3.47**	3.25**
Madhuri	-8.32**	-2.24	-0.16	3.26**	-8.07**

^a* and ** = significant at P.05 and P.01, respectively.

Table 2. Crosses showing specific combining ability effects for grain yield and other characters.^a

Cross	Plant height	Heading date	Tiller number	Test weight	Grain yield
V20 A/IR54	26.73**	7.03*	-5.44**	1.59	-3.60*
V20 A/Sattari	-9.73**	18.08**	-3.44*	-2.45*	-2.20
IR46829 A/Pankaj	1.73	11.29**	0.11	3.96**	-3.88**
IR46829 A/Sattari	6.21	-7.62*	2.18	-0.05	8.46**
IR46829 A/T26	-15.49**	6.49	2.70	3.82**	-3.26*
Z97 A/IR50	2.95	4.59	13.64**	0.05	-5.40**
Z97 A/IET5656	4.94	-4.96	6.10**	-4.00**	23.83**

^a* and ** = significant at P. 05 and P .01, respectively.

Only seven crosses showed high SCA effects for one or more characters (Table 2). V20 A/IR54 for tall and IR46829A/T26 for dwarf plant height; IR46829 A/Sattari for early heading; IR46829 A/Pankaj and IR46829 A/T26 for test weight; 297 A/IR50 for tiller number; and Z97 A/IET5656 for grain yield were the best specific combiners.

The parental lines 297 A and IET5656 had the highest GCA effects in their respective female and male groups for grain yield, and also produced the best SCA effect for grain yield. Crosses showing high SCA effects for plant height and tiller number involved parents of high and low GCA values; parents with high GCA values exhibited high SCA effect for earlier heading date in their crosses. Parents showing high SCA values in their crosses were low general combiners for test weight. The SCA effect was more common and pro-

nounced in crosses involving male fertility restorer lines with CMS lines.

The cross combination showing high SCA effect for grain yield also showed high SCA effect for tiller number, indicating tiller number is an important yield component. ■

Relationship of genetic variances of quantitative characters in indica rice to nitrogen level

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Genetic variance reflects the magnitude of the gene effect controlling certain characters. We studied the relationship of genetic variance of 12 characters to N

level in a field experiment in Tsukuba, Japan, May-Oct 1989. Indica rice varieties IR8, IR24, Milyang 23, Stipepe, Saturn, 68-1, Ch-47, Belle Patna, Guichao 2, and IR2061-214-3 were used. N levels were 0, 35, 70, and 105 kg N as urea/ha. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications, N in the main plots and variety in the subplots. Forty plants/variety were grown in each subplot, at 15- × 25-cm spacing. Quantitative characters were measured on the middle five plants in each subplot. Genetic variance of each character was estimated as

$$Vg = (MSg - MSe)/r$$

where *MSg* and *MSe* are the mean squares for genotype and error, and *r* the number of replications. The relationship of *Vg* and phenotypic mean for each character with N level was determined by correlation analysis (see table).

Correlation coefficients for genetic variance and phenotypic means of 12 characters with N levels.^a

Item	PH	DH	MTN	PN	ETP	TSN
P	-0.982*	-0.788	-0.977*	0.973*	-0.955*	-0.040
G	0.900	-0.957*	0.986*	0.987*	0.649	-0.075
	FSN	FSP	GW	GY	BY	HI
P	-0.895	-0.774	-0.972*	0.961*	0.969*	-0.983*
G	-0.709	0.953*	-0.525	0.888	0.812	-0.378

^aP = correlation coefficient between phenotypic mean and N level, G = correlation coefficient between genetic variance and N level, * = significant at 5% level. PH = plant height, DH = days to heading, MTN = maximum tiller no., PN = panicles/plant, ETP = effective tiller percentage, TSN = total spikelet no., FSN = filled spikelets/panicle, FSP = filled spikelet percentage, GW = 1,000-grain wt, GY = grain yield, BY = biological yield/plant, HI = harvest index.

Genetic responses to N did not always coincide with phenotypic response. The genetic variances of maximum tiller no. (MTN), panicles per plant (PN), and filled spikelets per panicle were positive and significantly correlated with N level. The genetic variance of days to heading (DH) was negative and significantly correlated with N level.

Genetic variation is the basis of rice breeding. It is easier to select for a certain character when its genetic variance is larger. In breeding indica rice, selecting for MTN, PN, and effective tiller percentage would be more efficient at higher N levels. But selecting for DH would be more efficient at lower N levels. ■

Contents of endogenous hormones GA, IAA, and ABA in semidwarf rice

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We measured the level of endogenous GA, IAA, and ABA in near-isogenic lines of indica rices.

Er-Jiu-Qing with *Sd₁* gene, Er-Jiu-Qing with *sd₁* gene, waxy Guang-Lu-Ai 4 with *Wx* gene, and nonwaxy Guang-Lu-Ai 4 with *wx* gene are near-isogenic lines with one gene difference. Four plant types are tall, dwarf a, dwarf b, and superdwarf, japonica type (derived from Jia 23/Xue-He-Ai-Zao (XHAZ) F₃) with *Sd₁Sd₁Sd₃Sd₃*, *sd₁sd₁Sd₃Sd₃*, *Sd₁Sd₁sd₃sd₃*, and *sd₁sd₁sd₃sd₃* genotypes, respectively, by genetic test of plant height and GA, response. Jia 23 (*sd₁* gene) and XHAZ (*sd₃* gene) were the check varieties.

Suge's method of assay and of extraction were used to evaluate hormone level in aboveground plant parts.

Contents of endogenous gibberellin-like substance were higher in tall plants

Table 1. Content of endogenous hormones of near-isogenic lines.^a

Variety	Genotype	Plant height (cm)	Hormone ^a (μg/kg fresh wt)		
			GA	IAA	ABA
Tall Er-Jiu-Qing	<i>Sd₁Sd₁</i>	128.0	1.68 a	0.58 a	0.35 c
Dwarf Er-Jiu-Qing	<i>sd₁sd₁</i>	75.0	1.13 c	0.11 c	0.97 a
Waxy Guang-Lu-Ai 4	<i>WxWx</i>	80.0	1.18 b	0.13 b	0.81 b
Nonwaxy Guang-Lu-Ai 4	<i>wxwx</i>	80.0	1.18 b	0.13 b	0.81 b

^aIn a column, means followed by different letters are significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Table 2. Content of endogenous hormones of near-isogenic plants with different dwarfing genes (μg/kg fresh wt).^a

Plant type	Genotype	Plant height (cm)	Hormone ^a (μg/kg fresh wt)		
			GA	IAA	ABA
Tall	<i>Sd₁Sd₁Sd₃Sd₃</i>	133.5	1.68 a	0.63 a	0.29 d
Dwarf a	<i>sd₁sd₁Sd₃Sd₃</i>	96.0	1.25 d	0.22 b	2.08 c
Dwarf b	<i>Sd₁Sd₁sd₃sd₃</i>	75.0	1.61 bc	0.14 e	2.29 a
Superdwarf	<i>sd₁sd₁sd₃sd₃</i>	45.0	1.57 c	0.09 f	2.32 a
Jia 23 (CK1)	<i>sd₁sd₁Sd₃Sd₃</i>	92.0	1.23 d	0.16 d	2.19 b
Xue-He-Ai-Zao (CK2)	<i>Sd₁Sd₁sd₃sd₃</i>	93.0	1.66 ab	0.19 c	2.16 b

^aIn a column, means followed by different letters are significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

and dwarf type with *sd₃* gene than in dwarf type with *sd₁* gene (Table 1,2). The dwarfs had higher ABA content and significantly lower IAA content than tall plants. *Wx* was not related to

endogenous GA, IAA, and ABA.

We suggest that dwarf plant height was not due to low GA. Low IAA content, however, was the critical factor. ■